

KARAKTERI STI KI NA RAZVOJOT NA METODOLOGI JATA NA I STRA@U- VAWATA VO DEFEKTOLOGI JATA

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Rezime

Tekstot ima cel da gi poka`e razvojni te tendencii na metodologijata na defektolo{ki te i strauvawa vo svetot i kaj nas, no i da go potencira znaeweto na metodolo{ koto osposobuvawe na defektolo{ kite kadri { to se educiraat na Filozofski ot fakultet vo Skopje.

Nau-nite soznanija, do koi doajame po pat na istrau vawe, se osnoven preduslov za unapreduvawe na defektolo{ kata teorija i praktika. Rezultati te od nau-nata rabota nekoga{ predizvikuvaat mali, nezna-itelni promeni, a nekoga{ donesuvaat radikalni presvrsti. Blagodarenie na nau-nite istrau vawa i soznanija, otfrleni se odredeni predrasudi { to vladee do 60-tite godini na minatiot vek; kako na primer, uveruvaweto deka mentalno retardirani te deca treba da bidat segregirani od drugite vo op{ testvoto, bi deji se opasni i neprijatelski nastroeni, ili, deka gluvi te deca ne treba da go u-at znakovni ot jazik za{ to nema da bidat motivirani da nau-at da -i taat od usni i pote{ko }e se adaptiraat. Pija`e i sorabotnicite od @enevskata {kola bile edni od prvite istrau va-i koi go nametnale sf a}aweto deka hendi kepiranoto dete ne e hendi kepirano na sekoe pole i deka ima potencijal { to mo`e i treba da se razviva so sistematska i organizirana rabota.

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TENDENCIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH IN THE SPECIAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The aim of the text is to point out the developmental tendencies in the research methodology of special education and rehabilitation worldwide and in our country and to emphasize the importance of methodological training of students in special education and rehabilitation at the Faculty of Philosophy in Skopje.

The achieved scientific knowledge through research is the fundamental pre-condition for development of special education and rehabilitation theory and practice. The results of the scientific work sometimes cause small, insignificant changes, but, at times, they make radical changes. Thank to the scientific researches and knowledge, certain prejudices were rejected. For example, in the sixth decade of the last century there was a strong prejudice that mentally retarded children should be segregated from the society as aggressive and unfriendly ones or the deaf children should not learn sign language because they would not be motivated to learn lip-reading and would hardly adapt. Piaget and his colleagues from Geneva institute were the pioneers in researching this field and they imposed their belief that handicapped children were not handicapped in each field and they had potentials that could be developed and improved by systematic and organized work.

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Nesporna e potrebata za iniciative na { to pogolem broj natamo{ ni istra`uvawa vo sferata na defektologijata, kako { to e potrebna i kritika analiza na ve}e realizirane istra`uvawa. Natamo{ ni ot razvoj na nau~nite istra`uvawa vo defektologijata treba da pretstavuva osnova za kreiranje na obrazovna politika za licata so invalidnost i za unapreduvawe na institucionalni otivonistiucionalni ot tretman na ova populacija.

Klu~ni zborovi: defektologija, metodologija, istra`uvawa, nau~na rabota.

Razvojot na edna nauka se zasnova vrz nau~ni soznanija i zakoni tosti do koi se doajaa so istra`uvawe na stvarnosta. Op{ testvenite fenomeni, a osobeno pojavite vo vospitani eto i obrazovani eto na licata so invalidnost, se slo`eni, dinami~ni, polifaktorni. Nivnoto prou~vawe e specifi~no, kompleksno i bara razviena metodologija na istra`uvawe, koja }e nudi metodi, postapki i instrumenti adekvatni na problemite { to se prou~vaat.

Metodologijata ni gi otkriva patite do nau~nite soznanija i navinite zavnivno sistemizirawe i gradewe novi teorii vo naukata. I ako ima tesna povrzanost me|u metodologijate na nekoj bliski nauki -kako { to se metodologija na defektologijata, pedagogijata, psihologijata, sociologijata -sepak, metodologijata za istra`uvawe vo defektologijata ima specifi~nosti. Taa prou~va kako op{tite metodolo{ki principii postapki mo`eda se primenat vo nau~no-istra`uvakata rabota vo defektologijata.

Metodologijata za istra`uvawe vo defektologijata e nau~na disciplina { to se zanimava so prou~vawe na patite zavnivno sistemizirawe vo teorija, so cel da se unapredi edukacijata i rehabilitacijata na licata so pre~ki vo razvojot.

It is important to initiate further researches in the field of special education and rehabilitation, as well as a critical analysis of realized researches.

Further development of the scientific research in special education and rehabilitation should be a base for education policy on people with disabilities and development of institutional and non-institutional treatment of this population.

Key words: special education and rehabilitation, methodology, research, scientific work.

The development of a science is based on scientific knowledge and laws acquired through researches of the reality. The social phenomenon, especially those of upbringing and education of people with disabilities are very complex, dynamic and poly-factorial. Their studies are specific, complex and require a developed research methodology which offers methods, procedures and instruments adequate for the issues of research.

The methodology reveals the paths to the scientific knowledge and ways of their systematization and creation of new scientific theories. Although there is a link between the methodologies of certain close sciences, such as methodology of special education and rehabilitation, pedagogy, psychology, sociology, still the research methodology in special education and rehabilitation has its specifics and studies the possibilities of implementation of general methodological principles and procedures in scientific and research works in special education and rehabilitation. *The research methodology in special education and rehabilitation is a scientific discipline which studies the ways towards scientific knowledge and their systematization in theory in order to improve the education and rehabilitation of people with developmental disabilities.*

Metodologijata za istra`uvawe vo defektologijata nema podolga tradicija kaj nas. Duri i vo razvieni te zemji taa u{ te nema takva avtonomnost ili originalnost kako metodologijate na neкои други nauki, tuku pove}e stanuva zbor za sintezi rawe na metodolo{kite soznanija i principi od srodnite nauki i nivno prisposobuvawe kon specifi~nostite na istra`uva-kata rabota vo defektologijata. Vakvi ot status na metodologijata za istra`uvawe vo defektologijata ima pozitivni strani, za{to preteranoto osamostojuvawe na metodologijata na koja bilo nauka doveduva do opasnost od metodolo{kifragmentarizam i onevozmo`uva prifa}awe na novite soznanija od srodnite nauki.

Sepak, metodologijata na defektologijata mora da se razviva soglasno nejzini ot predmet na prou-uvawe, a toa zna~i taa da razviva istra`uva-ki postapki, tehnik i instrumenti, prisposobeni na specifi~nostite kaj licata so invalidnost: uslovi te vo koi tie`iveat i deluvaat, heterogenosta i malubrojnosta na ova a populacija, posebnosta na sekoj slu~aj i tn.

Vo na{ata dr`ava vistinski ot razvoj na metodologijata za istra`uvawe vo defektologijata po~nuva so otvorawe defektolo{kistudii za edukatori za lica so pre~ki vo psihofizi~ki ot razvoj, vo po~etokot vo ramkite na Institutot za pedagogija, a potoa kako zaseben Institut za defektologija pri Filozofski ot fakultet vo Skopje. Sozdavaweto na Institutot za defektologija e rezultat na odamna prisutnata potreba za sozdavawe kadri koi stru~no }e mo`e da odgovarat na specifi~nite obrazovni potrebi na edna populacija. Ovie kadri se nositeli na razvojt na defektolo{kata nauka i na nejzinata metodologija. Izuvaweto metodolo{kipredmeti vo ramkite na diplomskite i postdiplomskite studii po defektologija na Filozofski ot fakultet vo Skopje ne podrazbira samo zapoznavawe na studentite so metodite i tehnikite za istra`uva~ka rabota, tuku ima cel kaj niv da razviva istra`uva~ka qubopitnost, da gi

The research methodology in special education and rehabilitation has not experienced a long tradition in our country. Even though it has not yet succeeded the autonomy and originality in the developed countries as the methodologies of some other sciences, it synthesizes the methodological knowledge and principle of similar sciences and their adaptation to the specifics of research work in special education and rehabilitation. Such status of research methodology in special education and rehabilitation has its positive sides since the exaggerated independence of the methodology of any science leads to danger of fragmented methodology and disables the acceptance of new knowledge of similar sciences. The methodology in special education and rehabilitation has to develop in accordance with its research objectives, which means to develop research procedures, techniques and instruments adapted to the specifics of people with disabilities: the conditions in which they live and work, having in mind that this population is specific, heterogeneous and sparse.

In our country, the real development of research methodology in special education and rehabilitation started with the opening of the studies in special education and rehabilitation for educators of people with psycho and physical developmental disabilities, at the beginning in the framework of the Institute of Pedagogy, and then as an independent Institute of Special Education and Rehabilitation at the Faculty of Philosophy in Skopje. The foundation of the Institute of Special Education and Rehabilitation is a result of needs of creating personnel who will respond to the specific education needs of a population. These personnel are the bearers of the development of special education and rehabilitation science and its methodology.

The study of methodological subjects in the framework of undergraduate and postgraduate studies in special education and rehabilitation at the Faculty of Philosophy in Skopje means not only informing the students on methods and techniques of research works,

pottiknuva za tragawe po novi znaewa, da gi u~i racionalno da mislat i deluvaat, da imaat kritiki stav kon novite soznanija i, pred sé, da gi osposobi za sopstveni, samostojni istra`uva~ki potfati. Toa, pak, podrazbira smisla za organizacija, ume{nost za argumentirawe i doka`uvawe, kako i poznavawe na metodolo{ki te principi i kriteriumi za istra`uva~ka rabota.

Iniciraweto na {to pogolem broj empiriski istra`uvawa vo sferata na defektologijata e preduslov za natamo{no razvivawe i unapreduvawe na defektolo{kata teorija i praktika.

Razvojni tendencii vo istra`uvawa~kat a rabota vo defektologijata od minatoto do denes

Postavenosta na sovremeni te defektolo{ki istra`uvawa se dol`i na pove}evekovnata tradicija i iskustvo {to istra`uvawa~ite go steknuvale so prou~uvawe na defektologijata i srodni te nauki, osobeno pedagogijata i psihologijata. Naredni ot tekst sodr`i kus istoriski osvrt na istra`uvawata i metodologijata {to bila koristenava vo izminatoto period, so cel da se poka`at razvojni te tendencii vo istra`uvawa~kata rabota od minatoto do denes. Karakteristikite na istra`uvawata vo podra~jeto na defektologijata }e ja prosledime niz pet istoriski periodi, vrz osnova na periodizacijata na francuski ot metodolog Lan~er (Gilbert De Landcheere).

1. Period do 1900 godina

Prvite misli za vospitani eto na deteto se zabele`eni u{te vo stara Grcija, no tie bile rezultat na spekulacija na filozofite od toa vreme, a ne na empiriski istra`uvawa. Presvrtni cakon induktivni ot pristap vo naukata napravil Bekon (1561-1626), tvrdej}i deka "nema ni {to vo razumot {to prethodno ne bilo vo setilata#

but developing their research curiosity, stimulating them towards new knowledge, teaching them to think and deal rationally, teaching them to have critical approach towards new knowledge, enabling them for their own independent research activities. This means sense for organization, skills for argumentation and proving, as well as knowledge of methodological principles and criteria for research work.

The initiation of great number of empiric researches in the sphere of special education and rehabilitation is a pre-condition for further development and improvement of special education and rehabilitation theory and practice.

Background information for developmental tendencies in the research work in special education and rehabilitation

The contemporary research in special education and rehabilitation is due to long lasting tradition and experience of researchers acquired through studies in special education and rehabilitation and similar sciences, especially pedagogy and psychology. The following text presents background information on research and methodology used through history in order to show the developmental tendencies of the research work. The research characteristics in the field of special education and rehabilitation are shown through five historical periods according to the French methodologist Gilebrt de Landcheere.

1. Period till 1900

The first thoughts on child's upbringing were noticed in ancient Greece, but they were speculations of philosophers of that time and not empiric researches. The change towards the science indicative approach was made by Beckon (1561-1626) stating that "there is nothing in the reason which was not in the senses previously".

Toa zna~i deka soznanijata za pojavi te treba da se rezul tat samo na spekul acija, na razmi sluvawe, tuku i na neposredno nabqduvawe i iskustvo. Prvi primeri za sistematsko prou~uvawe na detski ot razvoj sretnuvame na krajot od 18 vek. Toga{ ger manski ot lekar Tideman (Tiedemann) ja pravi prvata iscrpna bi ograf ska studija za deteto, po { to sledat i drugi. Prvite pozna~ajni empiriski istra`uvawa bile sprovedeni na sami ot kraj od 19 vek (Stenli Hol), koi inicirale niza istra`uvawa so eksperimentalen karakter, poznati pod imeto "eksperimentna pedagogija" i "eksperimentna psihologija". Pojavata na ovie istra`uvawa bila rezul tat na pove}evekovnoto pedago{ ko prakti ~no i teorisko iskustvo, no neposredno bile usloveni od razvojot na prirodni te nauki vo 19 vek. Vo fizi kata, bi ol ogijata i medi cinata ve}e se vr{ ele istra`uvawa od eksperimenten karakter. Se primenuvale nekoi vidovi testovi. Po~nala da se koristi statistikata i da se gradat koncepti za standardizacija.

Eden od pozna~ajni te istra`uva~i na premit ot od 19 kon 20 vek bil **Vund** (Vilhelm Wundt, 1832-1920), germanski psiholog, koj doktoriral na medicinski te nauki na univerzitetot vo Hajdelberg. Vund se zanimaval so fiziologija na setilata i nervnite procesi. Toj po~nal da vr{ i istra`uvawa od takov vid vo germanski te laboratorii po fizi ka. Vo 1879 godina vo Lajpcig (Leipzig) toj ja osnova *privat a laboratorija za eksperiment na psihologija*.

Vo ovoj period, vo razli~ni zemji se vra{ at pove}e istra`uva~ki zafati koi pak se osnova za natamo{ na pri mena na empiriskite istra`uvawa vo podra~jeto na pedagogijata i defektologijata:

- 1864 godina, **Fisher** (G. Fisher) vo knigata *Scalebook predlo`uva niza skali za procenka na znaewata i za sposobnosti te na u~enicite*;
- 1894 godina, **Rajs** (Rice) i zrabotuva prv test za pravopis;

That means that the knowledge of appearances is not the result only of speculation, thinking, but it is a result of direct observation and experience.

The first examples of systematic researches of children development are found at the end of the 18th century. Then, the German doctor Tiedemann made the first detailed biographical study of children and many others followed afterwards. The first more significant empiric researches were carried out at the very end of the 19th century (Stanly Hall) which initiated other researches with experimental characteristics known as "experimental pedagogy" and "experimental psychology". The appearance of these researches was a result of long-lasting pedagogical, practical and theoretical experience and they were even more directly caused by the development of natural sciences in the 19th century. At that time, researches with experimental characteristics were done in the field of physics, biology and medicine using some kinds of tests, statistics and building concepts of standardization.

One of more significant researchers at the turn of 19th toward 20th century was **Vilhelm Wundt** (1832-1920), a German psychologist, who became PhD in medical sciences at Heidelberg University. Wundt worked with physiology of senses and nervous processes and started such researches in German laboratories of physics. In 1879, in Leipzig, he founded *the first laboratory of experimental psychology*.

At this period, in different countries there were research activities which can be considered as base for further implementation of empiric researches in the field of pedagogy and special education and rehabilitation:

- 1864, **G. Fisher**, in his book *Scalebook* suggested scales for estimation of student's knowledge and abilities;
- 1894, **Rice** prepared the first test for spelling;

- 1896 godi na **[ajt en]** (Schuyten) vo Belgi ja objavuva izve{ taj za svoite istra` uvawa na vni mani eto kaj u~ili { ni te deca;
- 1898 godi na, **Laj** (Lay) predlo` uva da se razli kuvaat termini te "eksperimentna psihologija# i "eksperimentna pedagogija#, a zaedno so Mojman (Meumann) izdavaat spisanie pod toj naziv;
- 1904 godi na **Klapared** (Clapared), doktor i Vundov u~enik, ja osnova Laboratorijata za eksperimentna psihologija na univerzitetot vo @eneva, a podocna (1912) tamugo osnova i pro~ueniot Institut "@an @ak Ruso#;
- 1905 godi na **Bine** (Binet) osnovuva u~ili { na laboratorija vo Pariz. I stata godi na so Simon (Simon) ja izrabotuvaat Skalata za inteligencija. Ovoj test za op{ ta inteligencija se sostoi od niza zadani, koi spored slo` enosta na operacijite i intelektualnite barawa, se prispobeni na karakteristikite na razvojni te periodi kaj li ~nosta. Sekoja zadana odgovara na opredelen broj meseci na razvoj. I spitanikot { to } e gi re{ i site predvideni zadani za negovata vozrast, se kategorizira kako prose~no i intelligenten. Dokol ku i spitanikot uspee da re{ i zadani od narednata vozrast (meseci na razvoj), dobiva novi poeni i se kategorizira kako subjekt ~ii intelektualni sposobnosti se porazvieni od onie { to se karakteristi ~ni za konkretnata kalendarska vozrast. Na toj na~in se dobiva odnosot na mentalnata i kalendarskata vozrast na ispitanikot { to se izrazuva so koeficient na inteligencija. Bine-Simonovata skala, kako prv vistinski mentalen test, ima golemo vlijanie i e masovno pri faten { irum svetot. Vo Francija primenata na ovaa skala e osnova za golemata reforma na obrazovani eto { to bila sprovedena vo 1905 godina. Ovaa skala ima istorisko zna~ewe i za razvojot na defektolo{ kite istra` uvawa. Skalata, kako test za op{ ta inteligencija, bila primeneta vo porane{ nata Jugoslavija, i toa prvpat u{ te vo 20-ti te godi ni na 20 vek vo Domot za slepi
- 1896, **Schuyten** in Belgium published a report on his researches of school children attention;
- 1898, **Lay** suggested making difference between "experimental psychology" and "experimental pedagogy" and together with Meumann published a magazine;
- 1904, **Clapared**, a doctor and Wundt's student founded the Laboratory for experimental psychology at Geneva University, and later (1912) founded the well-known Jean Jack Rousseau Institute there;
- 1905, **Binet** founded the school laboratory in Paris. The same year, he together with Simon made the intelligence scale. This test of general intelligence is consisted of different tasks which, according to the complexity of operations and intellectual requirements, are adapted to the characteristics of personal development periods. Each task corresponds to certain number of months of development. The tested person who solves all anticipated tasks for his/her age is categorized as average intelligent. If the tested person succeeds in solving tasks from the next age (months of development), he/she gains new points and is categorized as a subject with more developed intellectual abilities compared to the characteristics for the actual calendar age. In this way, the relation between mental and calendar age of the tested person is achieved and is expressed with intelligence quotient. Binet-Simon scale, as the first real mental test has had a great influence and has been largely accepted worldwide. In France, the implementation of this scale was the base for the big education reform carried out in 1905. This scale has a historical importance for the development of special education and rehabilitation researches. The scale, as a test for general intelligence, was implemented in former Yugoslavia in the second decade of the 20th century in the Home of blind in Zemun.

vo Zemun, koga bila prevedena od ~e{ ki jazik. Vo 30-tite godini na minati ot vek d-r Borislav Stevanovi } od Belgrad vr{ i nejzi na revizi ja, a povtorno e standardi zirana vo 60-tite godini.

Vo ovoj peri od do 20 vek nemalo razvi ena mre` a od insti tucii za zgri` uvawe na licata so pre-ki vo razvojot. Toa ja ote` nuvalo istra` uva-kata rabota. Decata so posebni obrazovni potrebi vo najgol em del bile vospituvani doma, a op{ testvenata gri` a za niv bila svedena na povremeno inf ormi rawe na javnosta kako da se postapuva so ni v vo ni vni ot razvoj.

2. Period od 1900 do 1930 gpdina

Ovoj period go narekuvale "vr{ na empirijata. Prethodno spomenati te i drugi istra` uva-i po-nale mnogubrojni istra` uvawa. Se raboti na usovr{ uvawe na instrumenti te za mental no testi rawe. Se pravat modeli za vrednuvawe na nastavni te planovi i programi, se prou-uva transferot na ve` bawe itn. Vlijanie vrz razvojot na istra` uvawata vo def ektologijata vr{ i psihoanaliti ~koto u~ewe na Frojd, bi hejvi ori zmot na Votson i, pred se, kognitivisti ~kata teorija { to ja razviva @enevskata { kola (1918). Pija` e i negovite sorabotnici doa|aat do revolucio nerni soznani ja. Se javuva edno optimisti ~no sf a} awe deka hendi kepi ranoto dete ne e hendi kepi rano na site podra~ja, odnosno deka so pri mena na soodvetni metodi toa mo` e postojano da napreduva i da gi razviva onie sposobnosti koi mo` e da se razvijat. Pri toa za negovata akceleracija e presudno da se respekti raat kriti ~ni te fazi vo razvojot i, vo to~no odredeni peri odi, da se pri menuvaat soodvetni vospitno-obrazovni postapki, pri { to intenzivno treba da bide anga` iran i samiot subjekt. I stra` uvawata vo ovoj period dovele do zna~ajni soznani ja za toa kako se odvi va "pri rodni ot# razvoj, a kakvi se otstapuvawata od normal ni ot proces na razvi vawe i sozrevawe.

Edna op{ ta karakteri sti ka na ovoj peri od

It was translated from Check language. In the third decade of the last century, Dr. Borislav Stevanovikj from Belgrade made linguistic review and was standardized again in the sixties.

During this period, up to the 20th century, there was no developed network of institutions for care of people with developmental disabilities which made the research work difficult. The children with special needs education were educated at homes and the social care for them was reduced to periodical information of the public how to treat them throughout their development.

2. Period 1900 – 1930

This period is called “the peak” of empiricism. The researchers previously mentioned and others started numerous researches. A lot of work was devoted to improving the instruments for mental testing, creating models for estimation of teaching curriculums and programs, studying the transfer of exercises and so on. The research development of special education and rehabilitation was influenced by Freud psycho-analytic teachings, Watson behaviorism and, above all, cognitive theory developed by the Geneva school (1918). Piaget and his associates came to revolutionary knowledge. An optimistic opinion occurred that the disabled children were not disabled in all spheres, i.e., with implementation of appropriate methods they could progress and develop their abilities. It is crucial to respect the critical phases of development for their acceleration and to implement appropriate upbringing and education procedures at certain periods with intensive engagement of subjects in question. The researches from that period led to significant knowledge about the “natural” development and what deviations from normal process of development and maturity were like.

The general characteristic of this period is research

e kvantitativna orijentiranost na istraživanja. Primenata na statistiku treba da gi nadmine nedostaci na formalizam od minatosti op{testvenite istraživanja da gi napravi "nau~ni", kako {to se oni evo prirodne nauke.

3. Period od 1930 do 1960 godina

Ekonomskata kriza od 30-tite godini predviđiva kriza i vo istraživa~kata rabota poradi drasti~noto namaluvawe na sredstvata za istraživawe vo obrazovanieto. Vo Germanija, Italija i Japonija se rafaizamot, a vo Francija, [panija i drugi zemji se javuva socijalisti~koto dvi~ewe. Vo Vtorata svetska vojna i vo povenite godini povtorno bila onevozna kakva bilo poznajna rabota na ovoj plan. Vo Sovetskiot sojuz vo 1936 godini "pedagogijata" e zabraneta so dekret na Komunisti~kata partija i tova i šedodeka e Stalin na vlast. Vo ovoj period vo Evropa poserozno istraživawe se zabele`ani na @enevskata i Moskovskata {kola (Piaget i Vigotski).

Pod vlijani na psihanaliti~ari te me|u 1935 i 1945 godini ponuvaat istraživawa za vlijani na iskustvo od detstvo vrz razvoj i vladeveto na vrasni ot~ovek. Na primer, vr{eni se istraživawa za posledici te od nedostig od maj~ina nega voranoto detstvo vrz podocne`ni ot razvoj na li~nost, kako {to e odbivawe od doewe, `iveewe vo rastureni domovi, vo instiucii bez roditelii sl.

Vo SAD, Avstralija i [vedska, iako imalo podobri uslovi za rabota, nema nekoj zna~en napredok vo pedago{kite istraživawa. Glavno, se rabotelo za voenice ili za marketing potrebi. Me|u poznajnite istraživa~i od ova vreme mo`e da gi spomeneme Gilford i Osborn. Tie rabotele vrz razvawe tehni ki za kreativno mi sl ewe i testovi za kreativnost.

4. Period od 1960 do 1980 godina

Periodot od 1960 do 1980 godini mo`e da se

quantitative orientation. The implementation of statistics had to overcome the disadvantages of the formalism from the past and to make the social researches "scientific" as those from natural sciences.

3. Period 1930 – 1960

The economic crisis from the 30s caused crisis in research work due to drastic decrease of funds for researches in education. The fascism was born in Germany, Italy and Japan and socialistic movement occurred in France, Spain and other countries. No significant research work was possible during the Second World War, as well as in the postwar period. In the Soviet Union the "pedology" was banned in 1936 with a decree by the Communist party during the Stalin regime. This period in Europe is characterized with more serious researches performed by Geneva and Moscow schools (Piaget and Vigotsky).

In the period from 1935 till 1945 researches about the influence from childhood experience over adult development and behavior started, influenced by the psycho-analytics. For example: the researches were made on the consequences from lack of mother's care in early childhood over person's later development, such as weaning, living in disorganized homes, parentless institutions and so on.

Although there were better working conditions in USA, Australia and Sweden, there was no significant progress of pedagogical researches. The researches mainly were for military or marketing purposes. Gilford and Osborn could be mentioned as more prominent researchers of that time since they worked on development of creative thinking techniques and creative tests.

4. Period 1960 – 1980

The period 1960-1980 can be called "explosion" of

nare~e peri od na "eksplozija# na naukata i nezapameten razvoj na istra`uvawata. Se prezemaat ogromni zafati i se vlo`uvaat golemi investicii vo obrazovani eto, osobeno vo SAD kade { to se nastojuva da se fati ~ekor so Sovetski ot sojuz, koj prv lansi ra satel it vo vsel enata.

Intenzivnata nau~no-istra`uva~ka rabota vo ovoj peri od doveduva do novi soznani ja za karakteristikite i etapite na psihofizi~ki ot razvoj na li~nosta. Na primer, Bruner uka`uva na gol emi te kog niti vni potencijali vo ranata vozrast i vo na~ini te za ni vno kori stewe. Pove}emi na istra`uva~i (MekViker Hant, Blum i dr.) ja prou~uvaat inteligencijata i gi razbivaat dotoga{ nite zabludi vo vrska so mentalni te sposobnosti na ~ovekot. Slackin gi utvrduva "peri odi te na osetli vost# kaj deteto. Erickson zboruva za ramnote`a na telesni te, mentalni te i socijalni te vli jani ja i tn.

Vo 60-tite godini zakonski se regulira obrazovani eto na decata so pre~ki vo razvojt, pri { to i za ni v stanuva obvrzno osnovnoto obrazovani e. Vo relacija so ova, se pove}e se aktuel izi ra dvi `eweto za integracija na decata so pre~ki vo razvojt vo redovni ot sistem na obrazovani e. Ova zalagawe osobeno e zastapeno vo SAD, [vedska i drugi te razvieni zemji. Za taacel se inicirani timski istra`uvawa od interdisciplinaren karakter koi treba da gi ispi taat prednosti te na integracijata na decata so pre~ki vo razvojt vo sistemot na redovno { kol uvawe.

Defektolo{ki te istra`uvawa intenzivno se razvivaat i vo pravec na otkrivawe i identifikacija na decata so pre~ki vo razvojt, kako i razrabotuvawe na metode, tehnikite i instrumentite za dijagnostici rawe na aktuel noto ni vo na razvoj na deteto. Defektolo{ki te fakulteti i insti tucii te za specijalna edukacija rabotat vrz unapreduvawe na modelite za rabota so decata so posebni obrazovni potrebi i soglasno so toa, tie razvivaat i na~ini za ni vno eksperimentno vrednuvawe.

the science and unprecedented research development. Enormous investments and activities in education were undertaken, especially in USA with tendency to keep up the pace with the Soviet Union's first satellite launching.

The intensive scientific and research work led to new knowledge on the characteristics and phases of person's psycho-physical development. For example: Bruner indicated great cognitive potentials of early age and ways of their use, more researchers (MacWicker Hunt, Blum and others) studied the intelligence and changed the previous errors related to human mental abilities, Slackin established the child's "periods of sensitivity", Erickson talked about the balance of physical, mental and social influences and so on.

In the 60s, the education of children with developmental disabilities was legally regulated and the primary education became compulsory for them. In compliance with this, the movement for integration of children with developmental disabilities in formal educational system became more current. This tendency is significantly present in USA, Sweden and other developed countries. That initiated interdisciplinary team researches in order to examine the advantages of integration of children with developmental disabilities in the system of formal education.

Special education and rehabilitation researches intensively developed both in discovering and identifying children with developmental disabilities, as well as working out the methods, techniques and instruments for diagnosing current level of child's development. Special education and rehabilitation faculties and institutions develop he models of work with children special needs educatin and according to this they develop approaches for their experimental evaluation.

Op{ ta tendencija na istra`uvawata vo ovoj period e domnacijata na pozitivisti~kiot i nomoteti~kiot pristap. Vo najgolemit broj slu~ai se koristi kvantitativnata metodologija i tehnikite za testiranje, sistematsko nabquduvawe, anketirawe. Se razvivaat novi poslo`eni statisti~ki postapki. A pojavata na kompjuterite i nivnata masovna primena vo istra`uvawata ja olesnuva nivnata primena i obrabotkata na podatocite.

Sepak, neopozitivisti~kiot pristap i preteranata kvantifikacija na istra`uvawata naskoro doveduva do reakcija. Domnacijata na eksperimentniot i analiti~kiot pristap po~nuva da gi osiroma{uva op{ testvenite istra`uvawa, bidej{i ne mo`e da gi zeme vo vid slo`enite aspekti na ~ovekovoto odnesuvawa i nivnata uslovenost od sredinata. Sé pove}e se zagovara kvalitativen, celovit, hermeneuti~ki pristap, zasnovan vrz razbirawe, a ne vrz tolkuvawe, a koj, pokraj drugoto, }e ja prou~uva i problematikata na indivi duata (poedinicot) ili poedinata grupa.

5. Period od 1980 gdi na do denes

Kvantitativnite istra`uvawa od minatiot period prodol`uvaat da se primenuvaat i natamu, no ne so tolkav obem i intenzitet. Od 80-tite godini sé pozastapen stanuva **kvalitativniot** pristap. Te`i{teto na defektolo{kite istra`uvawa se pomestuva. i, namesto dijagnostici rawe, se odi kon otkrivawe na na~inite so koi mo`e da se presretnat potrebite na licata so pre~ki vo razvojot. Vo Britanija od 1981 godina donesen e akt za ovaa populacija da se narekuva "lica so specijalni obrazovni potrebi #.

Metodolozite vo svetot sé pove}e gi istaknuvaat prednostite na kvalitativnite istra`uvawa, osobeno koga se ima predvid specifi~nosta na populacijata {to se prou~uva vo ramkite na defektologijata; populacija koja e pomalubrojna, pote{k dostapna i heterogena.

The general tendency of this period research is domination of positivistic and nomotetic approach. In most cases quantitative methodology and techniques for testing, systematic observation, questionnaires are used. More complex statistical procedures have developed. Computers and their mass implementation in research alleviate their use and data processing.

However, the neo-positivistic approach and exaggerated quantification of researches soon provoked reaction. Domination of the experimental and analytic approach started to impoverish social researches because it could not take into consideration numerous and complex aspects of human behavior and how the environment influenced them. Qualitative, complete, hermeneutic approach, based on understanding but not on interpretation, which at the same time studied the problems of individuals, single person and single group, was recommended.

5. Period from 1980 till now

The quantitative researches from the past period continued to be implemented but not with such volume and intensity. From the 80s the **qualitative** approach has become more present. The focus of special education and rehabilitation researches has moved and instead of diagnosing, it has been directed towards discovering ways for meeting the needs of people with developmental disabilities. In Britain, in 1981 an act was brought and this population was called people with special education needs.

The methodologists worldwide have pointed out the advantages of qualitative researches, especially when the specifics of studied population in the framework of special education and rehabilitation is taken into consideration; the population that is limited, not so much assessable and heterogeneous.

Prou-uvaweto na masovni istorodni poja- vi, statisti ~koto zaklu-uvawe i general i- zacijata na zaklu-oci te, svojstveni za no- moteti ~ki ot, kvanti tati ven pristap ne soodvetstvuva na karakteri sti ki te na pri- meroci te koi, obi ~no, se koristat vo de- fektolo{ kite istra` uvawa, a koi se sve- deni na mali grupi subjekti, grupi { to se ekstremno heterogeni i pote{ ko dostapni. Tretmanot na subjekti te vo grupi te e kom- plexen, specifi ~en i razli ~en za sekoj poedi nec, kako { to se razli ~ni i speci- fi ~ni potrebi te na sekoja indi vi dua. Poradi ovie pri ~i ni primenata na kl asi ~- no-eksperi mental noto istra` uvawe ~esto stanuva neadekvatna ili nemo` na. Metodo- lo{ ki problemi se javuvaat pri formi ra- weto i izedna-uvaweto na grupi te vo eks- peri mentot, pri opredel uvaweto na rep- rezentati vnosta na pri merokot, a seto toa pri dru` eno so moralni problemi na vne- suvawe na eksperi mentni te f aktori koi mo` e da predizvikaat zna~itelni pozi- tivni ili negativni efekti kaj ispi- tani ci te. Ova se samo del od nedostatoci te i ograni ~enosti te na kvanti tati vni te is- tra` uvawa vo obl asta na def ekto lo gi ja ta, koi mo` e da bi dat nadmi nati so kval i ta- tivni ot pristap, odnosno so kombi ni rana pri mena na razli ~ni te i str a` uva ~ki stra- tegi i (metodolo{ ka tri angul aci ja).

I str a` uvawata vo podra ~jeto na def ek- to lo gi ja ta denes stojat vrz cvrsti osnovi i se razvivaat kako { to se razvi va def ek- to lo{ kata teori ja i prakti ka. Ni vni ot nau ~en status se dol ` i na dragoceni te soznani ja od i str a` uvawata vo i zmi nati te peri odi .

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The study of mass and homogeneous phenomena, statistical conclusion and generalization of conclu- sions, typical for nomothetic, quantitative ap- proach, does not relate to characteristics of the ex- amples used in special education and rehabilitation researches which are limited to small groups of subjects, groups that are extremely heterogeneous and hard to be assessed. The treatment of the sub- ject of groups is complex, specific and different for each individual as the needs of each individual are different and specific, too. Due to that, the imple- mentation of classical experimental research is often inadequate and impossible. The methodo- logical problems occur when the groups are formed and merged during the experiment while determining the sample representation, accompa- nished by ethical and moral issues of taking in ex- perimental factors that can cause significant posi- tive or negative effects on examined people. These are some of disadvantages and limitations of quantitative research in the field of special educa- tion and rehabilitation which can be overcome with the qualitative approach, i.e., with combined implementation of different research strategies (methodological triangulation).

The researches in the field of special education and rehabilitation stand on firm fundamentals and have developed together with special education and re- habilitation theory and practice. Their scientific status is a result of valuable research knowledge from the previous periods.

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